

Representation of Immigrant Identity in Bharati Mukherjee's Jasmine

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Abstract

This research paper is an attempt to excavate the role of identity which holds a prior position in the displacement and dislocation of the immigrant individuals. The diasporic communities settled outside their natal homelands act as passive victims buried deep down in the dominant adopted land. Indubitably the migrated individuals not only experience a degree of geographical and psychological alienation but are also subjected to an inescapable link with their homelands. There are numerous parameters to diasporic literature but one of the most celebrated one is identity. An immigrated individual always struggles between multiple locations and multiple identities. There is a constant state of flux to accommodate oneself under one identity. Through this paper, the novel's protagonist Jasmine's vulnerability in the adopted country and her existence with several names and manifold identities in heterogeneous environments is illuminated. The paper examines whether Jasmine, with her ever-changing identities, succeeds in negotiating assimilation within the host country or ultimately reveals a failure to integrate. The transformation of Jasmine's identity displays the entire immigrant experience. The perpetual remodelling of the character hauls from the peripheries to the centre of the dominant culture. The conflicts about identity faced by Jasmine and how she carves herself into the adopted society is evaluated in this paper. The trauma of dislocation and identity crisis in the postcolonial context play a vital role to shred the minute threads of Jasmine's plight in the novel. Recognizing the matter in question, the perspective highlighted is the voice of the female character unraveling her immigrant journey throughout the novel.

Keywords

Assimilation, Displacement, Diaspora, Identity, Immigrant.

Introduction

The issue of immigration is grave and widely studied in postcolonial studies. Individuals migrate to non-native lands do not only suffer displacement and dislocation, but also negotiate their identity. These diasporic communities on foreign lands in this context ultimately undergo geographical and psychological alienation. Several writers have illuminated this theme among whom Bharati Mukherjee's novel *Jasmine* holds a prominent position. In this novel, the protagonist Jasmine faces tragic episodes in her life before she decides to migrate to the United Nations. In that new country and alien culture, she lives through manifold identities and struggles to seek an identity which she can call her own and associate with. Mukherjee has captured the essence of her young protagonist's eternal struggle and the expectation to conform to the culture of the host country.

The paper investigates the construction and conflict of identity in *Jasmine* with special focus on the protagonist's journey and transformation across multiple contexts. It also explores and challenges cultural belongingness through experiences like displacements, trauma and hybridity. Informed by postcolonial theorists like Homi K. Bhabha, Stuart Hall, and Edward Said, the paper highlights the nuanced portrayal of the fragile yet resilient nature of immigrant identity and displacement that centrally aligns with the larger framework of diasporic literature.

Objective of study

The paper analyses Bharati Mukherjee's novel *Jasmine* through postcolonial and cultural theories that elucidate the multifaceted complexities of identity in relation to immigrant communities. Concerns and challenges like identity, isolation, displacement, alienation and assimilation are examined by theories professed by postcolonial thinkers such as Homi K. Bhabha's concept of hybridity which suggests that identities of immigrants emerge in the "third space" of enunciation, where different cultures intermingle and merge that lead to new forms of subjectivity (Bhabha 55). As Jasmine transforms herself into different personalities at every stage in her life, she advocates a narrative where cultural assimilation takes place.

Stuart Hall's idea of cultural identity in 'Cultural Identity and Diaspora' as "a matter of becoming as well as being" profoundly demonstrates the ever-evolving and fragmentary nature of immigrant subjectivity (Hall 402). The same can be seen in the novel *Jasmine* where her identity is perpetually changing. Edward Said on the subject of displacement, exile and trauma deliberates that they involve both loss and the potential for new

Review of Literature

affiliations (Said 173). In the same way, Jasmine too experiences both loss as well as the gained and re-gained potential to outgrow her previous stage of life by empowering herself to persist in progress. Analysing Mukherjee's work through this theoretical perspective, the reader will gain better comprehension about immigrant identity.

Within the diasporic literature, there are numerous concerns such as displacement, dislocation, homelessness, alienation, trauma, mimicry, hybridity, assimilation, identity and many others, that are reflected in works of many diasporic writers. This paper will extensively explore the 'identity' concern which is prevalent and dominant throughout the novel 'Jasmine'. Diasporic literature has already addressed and complicated the idea of identity for immigrants who have moved out of their homelands into foreign lands, struggled and adapted the new culture. Bharati Mukherjee's novels are conventionally read in the light of this framework. Through this paper, the issue of identity of Mukherjee's protagonist Jasmine is deeply studied and reflects her constant negotiation between becoming and unbecoming. It is even asserted that "Identity is an important issue in diasporic literature. Stuart Hall contends that identity should not be thought of as an accomplished fact, but should be seen as a production which is never complete." (Lal 27) Avtar Brah in his 'Cartographies of Diaspora' (1996) comments that "Diaspora space is the point at which boundaries of inclusion and exclusion, of belonging and otherness, of 'us' and 'them', are contested. My argument is that diaspora space as a conceptual category is 'inhabited', not only by those who have migrated and their descendants, but equally by those who are constructed and represented as indigenous." (Brah 208-9) Therefore, identity in terms of immigrant subjectivity becomes a hyphenated state of existence, constantly shifting between struggles of belongingness and otherness. There are many scholars who have portrayed identity in terms of female diasporic identity with regards to the young Indian girl Jasmine in Mukherjee's novel as Bharati Mukherjee has dramatized the shift of role and identity of Jasmine from being a village girl in Punjab to Jasmine to Jane and then to Jase and Jazzy. Thus, the paper will also highlight nuances of Jasmine's changing identities and her struggles during her transformation in the novel.

Main Text

Protagonist's Transformation: From Jasmine to Jyoti to Jase to Jazzy

At the outset of the novel *Jasmine*, "the protagonist Jyoti tells the story when she is twenty four years old. Jyoti is a poor peasant village girl born in the restricted feudal society of Hasnapur, Punjab State in India" (Mary S. 35). Her life in village was enveloped by patriarchal constraints and gender bias, where having a girl child was considered as bad as possessing a bad fate. She wanted to get educated but was denied her education because she was a girl, and only her brothers Aravind-Prar and Hari-Prar could avail this opportunity. She gets married to Prakash Vihj with whom she had plans to the United States. After Prakash's death, she moves abroad and renames herself as 'Jasmine' that is symbolic of the identity change and assimilation that any immigrant would want to undergo in order to survive. As Jasmine moves ahead in her journey in America, she becomes Jane in Iowa, Jase in New York, and later Jazzy in Florida. With every new name and new role, the transformative shifts reflect the fluidity of diasporic identity. Her multiplicity of selves exemplifies what Hall calls the "continuous play of history, culture, and power" in identity formation (Hall 394). In the novel *Jasmine*, the protagonist remarks:

In America, nothing lasts. I can say that now and it doesn't shock me, but I think it was the hardest lesson of all for me to learn. We arrive so eager to learn, to adjust, to participate, only to find the monuments are plastic, agreements are annulled. Nothing is forever, nothing is so terrible or so wonderful, that it won't disintegrate. (181)

Through Jasmine's journey, the reader identifies how immigrant women engage with, navigate through and cope with cultural hybridity while they oppose the patriarchal structure of oppression and domination.

Trauma, Displacement, and the Female Immigrant

Trauma and displacement are the core themes of diasporic literature. Immigration is not just geographical, away from one's motherland to a foreign land, but also a psychological one, where culture shock is predominant. The novel's protagonist has varied experiences from being a widow, to illegally migrating to the United Nations, the sexual abuse she faces in the non-native land, and most importantly the cultural alienation. Summing up all these experiences, she becomes the central figure in elucidating the displacement an immigrant goes through. Despite her struggle, Jasmine's individuality is read as fluid and adaptable from the postcolonial vantage point. From the lens of a female immigrant, her body becomes the site of multiple violations and transformations, yet she is showcased as a strong and resilient woman.

Highlighting the struggles of a female immigrant, it can be analysed that Jasmine was doubly marginalized. Being an immigrant, she was deprived of home and belongingness, and being a woman, void of basic dignity. She becomes the victim, both in India as well as America. She kills Half-Face, the man who assaults her upon her arrival in the United States. This particular incident fosters courage in her to refuse to remain quiet and she then decides to transform her immigrant self. She gains economic independence by

working as a nanny to Duff. Her entire journey in the novel highlight her reinvention. As Renu Jason in his essay "A Study in Globalization Alienation and Quest for identity" assert:

Having undergone an alarming experiences and integrating herself with every changing condition and expectation, she emerges as a character ready to change her destiny and explore infinite possibilities to assert her identity in the alien land. But this change is not without pain, because every time she feels that her identity and her own values are in a clash with the outward social values. Jasmine shows the ability to adapt and survive in a foreign land and her views about marriage and love undergo a great change. (76)

Identity and Assimilation

Identity is a widely discussed concern in immigrant literature. With close reading of the novel, it can be stated that Jasmine embodies what Stuart Hall describes identity as, a "production which is never complete, always in process" (Hall 402). This brings the issue of assimilation to the foreground. One of the main questions in the novel arises for the protagonist whether she, being an immigrant, could assimilate in the adopted culture of American society or whether she remains alienated throughout her life. She as an immigrant character is shown to have made efforts to adapt to newer identities and new places. For instance, Jasmine becomes Jane Ripplemeyer in Iowa, accepting small-town American life, and later, as Jase in New York, she embodies cosmopolitan spirit. Her perpetual transformation also emphasizes on her unstable identity and uprooted belongingness. Far away from her original home, she seeks abode everywhere she goes. Her idea of home, like her identity, is fluid and constantly renegotiated. There is no centrality in the notion of home, it is always scattered, unstable and dynamic. Her constant urge to be somewhere and become someone, refusal to remain static reflects what Bhabha calls the "third space" of cultural negotiation (Bhabha 56). This is where Homi Bhabha's concept of hybridity comes alive when the immigrant lives in-between the space. The young individual's identity and existence oscillates between her homeland India and her migrant land America, and she tries to assimilate herself in an in-between space of survival.

Jasmine's (Un)Settled Identity

The novelist presents the protagonist as someone who has lived through uncertainty and unsettlement throughout the story. Jasmine's identity has been circled by alienation and depicted in multiple selves. Jasmine became herself from Jyoti which further led to her becoming Jane, Jase and Jazzy, thus, questioning her ability to survive in the dominant adopted land and portraying her constant reinvention for survival. In the novel, Jasmine says that she had a husband for each of the women she has been, Prakash for Jasmine, Taylor for Jase, Bud for Jane, Half-Face for Kali. She phrases the development of these identities in a manner which suggests that she has chosen a husband for each self, rather than her husbands themselves influencing the creation of Jasmine's selves, the tension that results from this contradiction is indicative of Jasmine's constant battle with the situations throughout the novel. (S 111)

This highlights much more about Jasmine and the way she is presented by Bharati Mukherjee. It shows her strength, forward looking approach, acceptance for new possibilities, and motivation to empower and adapt, despite the fragmentation and fractured immigrant self. She is continuously creating and re-creating herself.

Conclusion

To sum up, Mukherjee's novel *Jasmine* is suggestive of immigrant identity being ever-evolving, fluid and dynamic. The protagonist underwent multiple transformations from the very beginning till the end of the novel, thus reflecting that identity is and will always be a perpetual negotiation of metamorphosis. The novel is a complex exploration in defining her belongingness since her everyday life revolves around displacement, trauma and assimilation. The young individual's story contributes to discourses, both postcolonial and feminist. By analysing the work through the lens of theories on cultural identity, diaspora space and hybridity, it can be rightly concluded that Jasmine has upheld the standards of a resilient woman, showcasing strength in whatever identity she lived through despite all the challenges and instability which the dominant culture had to offer. She navigated her immigrant life through integration and assimilation.

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